

OUTCOMES OF SCHOOL ROLES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CIVIC ENGAGEMENT OF GRADUATES FROM PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

Civic engagement is making a significant and positive difference. Through civic engagement, adolescents can increase community vitality, challenge injustices, and address social problems. This study attempted to identify the outcomes of the school roles in the development of civic engagement of graduates from public secondary school respondents. A self-made questionnaire was used, and data gathered from 293 public secondary school graduates was analyzed and interpreted using Chi-Squared and Spearman's Correlation Test. Results showed a significant relationship between the personal profile and the extent of school roles among the graduates of public secondary school respondents, Cooperative Learning, Academic Success, and Grading System was found to be significant with their profiles. Although none of the personal profiles was significant to discipline practices and social support in school. All the civic engagements participated in by the respondents have a relationship with their profile. In the test of relationship between the extent of school roles and the level of civic engagement among the graduates of public secondary school respondents as outcomes of school roles orientation, almost all the variables tested were found to have a significant relationship with the other variable. This study also implies that the meaningful experience derived from school activities are life-long memories of the graduates which become their luminaries in accomplishing tasks, performing their duties, and achieving their dreams. It is recommended that the results of this study be presented to the top management of the Schools Division Office of Laguna to come up on a program intensifying civic engagements since it was found that these are significantly related to their previous school roles.

Keywords: *Civic Engagement, Civic Skill, Cooperative Learning, Disciplinary Practices, School Roles, Social Cohesion*

INTRODUCTION

In modern communities, the prejudice about the social differences of individuals and groups makes it difficult to think and act to create contexts of responsible ways of togetherness (Stornaiuolo and Thomas, 2017), in addition to this, a much critical matter is presented in a study that through collective civic engagement, a better and responsive community and government is produced. Indeed, civic engagement represents a key element in creating social relationships and developing a sense of responsible and responsive togetherness because it promotes prosocial values and increases active citizenship and sense of community (Procentese et al. 2019). In the sense of the value of producing civically engaged citizens comes the value of secondary schools' activities' parallelism towards this goal which means it is important to assess and properly respond to the goal of the curriculum in connection with the purpose of producing a civically engaged citizens.

Civic engagement refers to prosocial and political contributions to community and society (Wray- Lake et al, 2017). Civic engagement goes beyond behaviors and includes psychological dimensions such as values, beliefs, attitudes, skills, and knowledge (Wray-Lake and Abrams, 2020). It is an essential type of engagement as it is powered by the community itself and is most often a combination of marginalized and those elevated members of the community — an inclusive and diverse group that is serving a diverse group of goals relevant to the communities' needs. Citizens' civic engagement can represent a key issue and a solution to rely on to pursue this aim and promote what is here defined as the sense of responsible togetherness: it brings people of the community toward spaces wherein community relationships can be built and managed, and community dialogue and confrontation can be carried forward, thus becoming the basis for collective actions based on shared purposes.

On another note, how are civically engaged citizens produced? If this type of engagement is essential, it is also therefore vital to understand how civically engaged citizens are produced. Some among these are programs and training conducted by the government and community, another is the habits built from home and parenting, next is the different school activities and lessons taught at school (Blevins et. al., 2016). In much research, results show how significant the school roles are in producing civically engaged citizens and even while still spending their time at school, it is believed that students are already working in activities that makes them civically engaged. Research showed that the activism of 10th graders (ages 15–16) involved in a youth participatory action research (YPAR) project resulted in a clear need for interventions aiming to foster new ways of living together within local communities and rebuild individuals' sense of responsibility toward them (DeJaynes and Curmi-Hall, 2019). This research showed how students are

totally civically engaged in identifying needs and ways to resolve matters related to this issue in a civically engaged manner.

DeJaynes and Curmi (2015) described and believed that young people are culturally and intellectually engaged global citizens, or cosmopolitan intellectuals. Youth volunteers for numerous causes or organizations, help their neighbors informally, participate in political campaigns, advocate to improve their schools and communities, engage in protests, and work to protect the environment. These youthful activities will reveal how schools develop civic skills and their relationship with current career paths.

On the other hand, everyone focuses on one's own problems as they are solely private and tries to solve them with one's own resources (Doolittle and Faul, 2013). The citizens seem not interested in collective actions or social debates and delegate others to administer common things, with the development of low levels of civic engagement that makes it difficult to produce collective and volunteering actions within local communities.

Moreover, instances from research resulted on how civic engagement may have been giving important beneficence and is correlated with the education's activities and lessons, yet only few numbers of research presented rates and results of the presence of actual civic engagement in the community. In a study, by Dubow et. al. (2017), it shows how technology is now being integrated in developing training and activities related to producing civically engaged citizens as well as having actual civically engaged citizens. This proves that there might be disparity with the seeded activities for the development of behaviors and actions related to civic engagement and actual number of civically engaged citizens as well as the results of its benefactions.

Based on the above-mentioned studies and repercussions, this research aims to understand the contribution of school roles in the development of civic engagement, in terms of both attitudes and behaviors, which may help in promoting their sense of responsible togetherness, which can foster new ways of living together within local communities.

Research Questions

Specifically, the study seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the personal profile of the graduates of public secondary schools, in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Gender;
 - 1.3 Public Secondary School attended;
 - 1.4 Awards received, and
 - 1.5 Types of Civic Engagement?

2. What is the extent of school roles as perceived by graduates of public secondary school respondents, in terms of:
 - 2.1 Cooperative Learning;
 - 2.2 Disciplinary Practices;

- 2.3 Academic Success;
 - 2.4 Grading System;
 - 2.5 Social Support, and
 - 2.6 Other School Activities?
3. What is the level of civic engagement of graduates of public secondary school respondents as outcomes of school roles with respect to civic engagements in terms of:
 - 3.1 Civic Action;
 - 3.2 Civic Commitment (Duty);
 - 3.3 Civic Skills, and
 - 3.4 Social Cohesions?
 4. Is there a significant relationship between the personal profile and the extent of school roles among the graduates of public secondary school respondents?
 5. Is there a significant relationship between the personal profile and the level of civic engagement among the graduates of public secondary school respondents as outcomes of school roles?
 6. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of school roles and the level of civic engagement among the graduates of public secondary school respondents as outcomes of school roles?
 7. What is the meaningful experience/experiences of the graduates of public secondary school respondents relevant to their civic engagement?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized descriptive correlational method to find out the Outcomes of School Roles in the Development of Civic Engagement of Graduates from Public Secondary School. Respondents were the graduates of the public secondary schools in the Division of Laguna which includes sub-offices of Siniloan, Famy, Mabitac and Santa Maria. The respondents were purposively chosen. They were the secondary school graduates who are actively engaged and continuously taking part in civic engagements. The researcher developed a self-made questionnaire. On the validity and reliability of the questionnaire, it passed the evaluation of the experts.

For this study to arrive at the most valuable answers and analysis, the following statistical tools and treatment was used:

This study used frequency and percentage in answering the personal profile of the learners, in terms of age, gender, public secondary school that they attended, awards received and type of their civic engagement.

In answering the questions about the evaluation of the extent of school roles as experienced by the respondents during their high school. It includes aspects like cooperative learning, disciplinary practices, academic success, grading system, social support, and school activities. The last part was the level of civic engagement of the students as outcomes of school roles. It includes aspects of civic action, civic commitment or duty, social cohesion, and civic skills. The author used the Likert Scale and weighted mean.

Spearman Rank Order Correlation and Chi-Square Test was used in analyzing and interpreting the relationships between the following: personal profile and the extent of school roles among the graduates of public secondary school respondents, the personal profile and the level of civic engagement among the graduates of public secondary school respondents as outcomes of school roles orientation, and the extent of school roles and the level of civic engagement among the graduates of public secondary school respondents as outcomes of school roles.

The last part of the questionnaire focuses on the meaningful experience/experiences of the respondents. For a more detailed analysis, the author used thematic analysis to analyze and interpret the responses of the respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Personal Profile of the Respondents

The survey conducted resulted in the distribution of respondents in terms of age as shown in Table 1. Highest frequency is 120 (41.00%) out of 293 whose ages is between 18 to 25 years old. Female respondents have a total of 137 (46.80%), male respondents have a total of 149 (50.90%), and some respondents who preferred not to say their gender has a total of 7 (2.40%). Total number of 293 graduate respondents from different public secondary schools participated highest number of respondents were from Famy NIHS, Gaudencio Octavio IHS, Gov. F.T. San Luis Nat'l. Agro- Industrial IHS, J. Santiago IHS, Mabitac INHS, Paagahan INHS, Siniloan INHS, and Sta. Maria IHS. Least number of respondents were from PINHS San Miguel Extension.

Learners who engage in civic actions need not to be on top of the class. Civic engagements of learners through experiential learning helped them develop higher understanding and wisdom. This current study showed an almost equal participation of honor and non-honor students. On the participation to different types of civic engagement is presented and it significantly specified activities may vary in terms of intensity of participation. For instance, in this study, a notable number of participants has a combination of the type of civic engagement with a total of 129 out of 293 (44.00%). This means that people are engage in different types of civic engagement for diverse reasons, including personal interests, a sense of duty, desires for social change, community connection, personal growth, and response to immediate change. In the study of Baldasser and Ramakrishnan, (2004) In terms of demographic characteristics other than

race and ethnicity, the highest levels of participation in civic activities are those based on education, homeownership, gender, and income.

Table 1. Distribution of Personal Profiles of the Graduate Respondents

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
18 to 25	120	41.00
26 to 33	93	31.70
34 and above	80	27.30
Total	293	100.00
GENDER	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Female	137	46.80
Male	149	50.90
Prefer not to Say	7	2.40
Total	293	100.00
SCHOOL ATTENDED	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Calangay HIS	13	4.40
Famy NIHS	30	10.20
Famy NIHS- Mayatba Extension	10	3.40
Gaudencio Octavio HIS	30	10.20
Gov. F.T. San Luis Nat'l. Agro-Industrial IHS	30	10.20
J. Santiago HIS	30	10.20
Mabitac INHS	30	10.20
Matalatala INHS	20	6.80
Paagahan INHS	30	10.20
Paagahan INHS- San Miguel Extension	10	3.40
Siniloan INHS	30	10.20
Sta. Maria HIS	30	10.20
Total	293	100.00
AWARDS RECEIVED	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Without Awards	147	50.20
With Honors	146	49.80
Total	293	100.00
TYPE OF CIVIC ENGAGEMENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Activism and Advocacy	11	3.80
Community Education and Awareness	12	4.10
Political Engagement	46	15.70

Community Service and Volunteerism	83	28.30
Philanthropy/ Fundraising	12	4.10
Combinations	129	44.00
Total	293	100.00

Extent of School Roles as perceived by Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents

In table 2, it was implied that listening and speaking skills have the highest extent and the lowest extent is collaborating with each other and giving constructive feedback. The computed average weighted mean was 4.52 and was interpreted as to a very high extent. This means that the respondents are very open to work on dialogue, listening skills, and debate, open to share ideas, knowledge, and points of view with classmates, willing to talk and give the same amount of time to explain. Willing to help each other to do the tasks, and prepared to talk about work to assess, correct, and improve it.

The very high extent interpretation was strengthened with the study of Malazonia et al., (2023) that stated collaborative learning process promotes both the democratic culture of the school and the social and civic competency of the students.

Table 2. Extent of School Roles in Terms of Cooperative Learning

Components of Cooperative Learning of the Respondents	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. work on dialogue, listening skills, and debate.	4.65	Very High Extent	1
2. share ideas, knowledge, and points of view with classmates.	4.53	Very High Extent	2
3. talk and give the same amount of time to explain.	4.52	Very High Extent	3
4. help each other to do the tasks.	4.45	High Extent	4.5
5. talk about work to assess, correct, and improve it.	4.45	High Extent	4.5
Average Weighted Mean	4.52	Very High Extent	

In Table 3, the extent of school roles in terms of disciplinary actions has an average weighted mean of 4.48 interpreted as having a high extent. This means that disciplinary

practices have a high extent on the respondents on the duration of their high school, these practices include disciplining, particularly giving advice, encouraging positively, understanding my point of view, expressing love, and enforcing punishment for wrong doings.

It is anchored in the study of Savitz et al., (2021) in which demonstrated that an increased focus of teachers on student-led learning through disciplinary practices, highlights how teachers made incremental changes that prioritized students' argumentation skills and comfort in sharing their voice throughout the debate process and beyond.

Table 3. Extent of School Roles in Terms of Disciplinary Practices

Components of Disciplinary Practices of the Respondents	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Give advice	4.56	Very High Extent	1
2. Encourage positively	4.50	Very High Extent	2
3. Understands my point of view	4.48	High Extent	3
4. Express love	4.44	High Extent	4
5. Enforces punishment for wrong doings	4.40	High Extent	5
Average Weighted Mean	4.48	High Extent	

In table 4, the average weighted mean was 4.46 interpreted as high extent. This implied that the total school experiences were satisfying, allowed them to become persistent in completing the grade level, helped in acquiring critical thinking skills, engaged on affective outcomes, and academic success was attained.

In the study of Philippe et al., (2023) it was revealed that both civic and non-civic organized activities independently predicted increases in GPA over the school year, even after adjusting for all covariables.

Table 4. Extent of School Roles in Terms of Academic Success

Components of Academic Success of the Respondents	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Satisfied with my over-all school experience.	4.52	Very High Extent	1
2. Persistent to complete the grade level.	4.46	High Extent	2.5

3. Able to acquire critical thinking skills.	4.45	High Extent	4
4. Able to engage on affective outcomes	4.41	High Extent	5
5. Able to attain academic success thru school.	4.46	High Extent	2.5
Average Weighted Mean	4.46	High Extent	

In table 5, the average weighted mean of 4.50 is interpreted to a very high extent. This implied a comprehensive, accurate, promotes growth and mastery of student learning and development, has a positive impact on learning, and include feedback that is a shared responsibility of the school, teachers, students, and parents of the grading system.

Based on Lee (2020), the development of such complex knowledge must be distributed across the K–12 public education sector: not limited to civics classes but distributed across all the disciplines taught in schools to promotes growth and mastery of student learning.

Table 5. Extent of School Roles in Terms of Grading System

Components of Grading System of the Respondents	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. is holistic (comprehensive).	4.58	Very High Extent	1
2. is authentic (accurate).	4.53	Very High Extent	2
3. promotes growth and mastery of student learning and development.	4.44	High Extent	5
4. has a positive impact on learning.	4.47	High Extent	4
5. include feedback that is a shared responsibility of the school, teachers, students, and parents.	4.49	High Extent	3
Average Weighted Mean	4.50	Very High Extent	

Table 6 shows that social support in school has an average weighted mean of 4.54 with an interpretation of very high extent. It implies that social support like showing appreciation, providing support, keeping communication lines open, supporting success affects, and respecting needs and limits, the students felt overwhelmed.

Based on (Chen et al., 2024) perceived social support and positive personality could mediate the chain between school climate and growth mindset of junior high school students.

Table 6. Extent of School Roles in Terms of Social Support in School

Components of Social Support in School of the Respondents	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. show appreciation.	4.65	Very High Extent	1
2. provide support when needed.	4.53	Very High Extent	2
3. keep communication lines open.	4.52	Very High Extent	3
4. supports success.	4.51	Very High Extent	4
5. respects needs and limits.	4.48	High Extent	5
Average Weighted Mean	4.54	Very High Extent	

In table 7 it reveals that the computed average weighted mean for this element is 4.58 with an interpretation of very high extent. This denotes those activities like election, festival of talents, sports competition, health, and wellness activities, also examinations and assessments were eagerly participated in by the respondents and influences them.

According to the study (Cahyono et al., 2023) leadership education in schools is an important strategy in building a generation of qualified leaders. To achieve this goal, a comprehensive and integrated programmed is needed in the school curriculum such as instilling leadership values early on, providing leadership training to students, creating mentoring and self-development programmed, and encouraging students to be involved in leadership activities at school.

Table 7. Extent of School Roles in Terms of Other School Activities

Components of Other School Activities of the Respondents	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Election of officers for different student organizations.	4.70	Very High Extent	1
2. Festival of Talents.	4.51	Very High Extent	5
3. Sports Competitions.	4.56	Very High Extent	3

4. Activities related to health and wellness.	4.52	Very High Extent	4
5. National Examinations and Assessments.	4.61	Very High Extent	2
Average Weighted Mean	4.58	Very High Extent	

Level of Civic Engagement

The starting point of this current study is focused on the role of civic education and civic engagement. Civic engagement and civic action, as it led to youth empowerment and long-term positive effects on social issues, wellbeing's, creativity, intelligence, democratic behaviors, all of which contribute to civic development.

As the data gathered were computed, results of the level of civic engagement as outcomes of school roles orientation in terms of civic actions has an average weighted mean of 4.42 which was interpreted at a high level. Civic actions implies that community volunteerism has helped me know a lot about opportunities to become involved in the community and contribute to improving life in my community, thus increasing my motivation to participate in advocacy or political action groups, made me intend to be involved in volunteer service, made me want to dedicate my career to improving society, and lastly helped me develop a sense of who I am, which now includes a sincere desire to be of services to others.

According to (Panni et al., 2023) it is recommended to educate students about service learning, and formally train their students for undertaking community projects, with practical suggestions for promoting civic engagement through community service for a sustainable future.

Table 8. Level of Civic Engagement as Outcomes of School Roles in Terms of Civic Actions

Components of Civic Actions of the Respondents	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
<i>(Community Volunteerism)</i>			
1. Helped me know a lot about opportunities to become involved in the community and contribute to improving life in my community.	4.53	Very High Level	1
2. Increased my motivation to participate in advocacy or political action groups after I graduate.	4.40	High Level	3

3. Made me intend to be involved in volunteer service after I graduated.	4.43	High Level	2
4. Made me want to dedicate my career to improving society.	4.38	High Level	4
5. Helped me develop a sense of who I am, which now includes a sincere desire to be of services to others.	4.38	High Level	5
Average Weighted Mean	4.42	High Level	

Table 9 shows the level of civic engagement as outcomes of school roles in terms of civic commitment, particularly community improvement, participation, and voting have an average weighted mean of 4.34 and is interpreted having high level. This implies that through civic engagements respondents realized that it is important to vote and be politically involved. They also prefer staying updated with current with the local and national news. They also make initiatives that will improve the community, and to have a deep conviction in my career goals to achieve purposes beyond my own self-interest.

Based on the study of (Tzankova et al., 2023), the importance of opportunities for active involvement and critical reflection in fostering interest, efficacy, and all forms of participation activities. The Democratic school climate was found to positively impact institutional trust and efficacy, but not participation.

Table 9. Level of Civic Engagement as Outcomes of School Roles in Terms of Civic Commitment

Components of Civic Commitment of the Respondents	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
<i>(Community Improvement, Participation, and Voting)</i>			
1. Helped me realize that it is important for me to vote and be politically involved.	4.51	Very High Level	1
2. Made me plan to stay current with the local and national news after I graduate.	4.23	High Level	5
3. Enabled me to plan or help implement an initiative that improves the community.	4.32	High Level	3
4. Made me feel a deep conviction in my career goals to achieve purposes beyond my own self-interest.	4.28	High Level	4

5. Motivated me to stay up to date on the current political issues in the community.	4.35	High Level	2
Average Weighted Mean	4.34	High Level	

Table 10 reveals that this study also aimed at determining the level of civic engagement as outcomes of school roles in terms of civic skills, particularly involvement in the civil society and this was computed to have an average weighted mean of 4.39 with a verbal interpretation of high level. This implies that thru civic engagements respondents were able to discuss controversial social issues with civility and respect with others openly, sharing their own thoughts and ideas. It is way of realizing that when members do not agree on how to solve a problem, they will likely arrive at a compromise.

Civic education has focused on preparing students to influence politics and government policy. Less attention has been paid to the curricular implications of civil society. Schools should be acquainting students with the knowledge necessary to evaluate the work of such organizations, as well as providing students with experience in the kinds of collaborative deliberation that takes place there (Ho and Barton, 2020).

Table 10. Level of Civic Engagement as Outcomes of School Roles in Terms of Civic Skills

Components of Civic Skills of the Respondents	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
<i>(Involvement in Civil Society)</i>			
1. Helped me discuss controversial social issues with civility and respect.	4.48	High Level	1
2. Helped me realize that when members of my group disagree on how to solve a problem, I like to try to build consensus.	4.33	High Level	5
3. Made me believe that I have a responsibility to use the knowledge that I have gained at school to serve others.	4.41	High Level	2
4. Prepared me to listen to others and understand their perspective on controversial issues.	4.35	High Level	4
5. Made me feel confident that I will be able to apply what I have learned in my classes to solve real problems in society.	4.38	High Level	3

Average Weighted Mean	4.39	High Level
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For the level of civic engagement as outcomes of school roles in terms of social cohesion, particularly in terms of cultural awareness, diversity and inclusion programming, the average weighted mean is 4.33 with an interpretation of high level. It only implies that community issues and concerns are dealt with professionally and accepts diverse ideas by the respondents and more likely made them to convince others to agree with their point of view.

Taken as a whole, civic engagement, at each analytical level, is usually regarded as a good, and necessary quality for making democracies stronger, strengthening the communities, and creating the sense of being felt. A positive role in the community can strengthen democracy, such as a vibrant civil society and fabric of fundamental societal values (Dawes et al., 2015).

Table 11. Level of Civic Engagement as Outcomes of School Roles in Terms of Social Cohesion

Components of Social Cohesion of the Respondents	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
<i>(Cultural Awareness, Diversity, and Inclusion Programming)</i>			
1. Has given me the professional knowledge and skills that I need to help address community issues	4.43	High Level	1
2. Helped make me a good listener, even when peoples' opinions are different from mine.	4.31	High Level	3
3. Made me believe that my community is enriched by having some cultural or ethnic diversity.	4.33	High Level	2
4. Helped me develop my ability to respond to others with empathy, regardless of their backgrounds.	4.29	High Level	4
5. Made me persuade others to agree with my point of view.	4.26	High Level	5

Relationship Between the Personal Profile and the Extent of School Roles among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents

In table 12, relationship between the personal profile and the extent of school roles among the graduates of public secondary school respondents in terms of cooperative learning was tested using chi- square test. Significant relationships were established on profiles such as age, school attended, and type of civic engagements. Tailoring cooperative learning activities to the developmental stage and interests of the learners can significantly enhance the effectiveness and enjoyment of the learning process. It is also seen that school attended has a significant relationship with cooperative learning which implies that school create a supportive and well-resourced environment for cooperative learning can foster more effective and enriching educational experiences for their students. And lastly, in types of civic engagement it infers that integrating various types of civic engagement into cooperative learning it prepares students for both academic success, active and informed citizens.

In the article by Akhrif et al., (2020) cited key criteria that assess intelligent collaboration and that serve to improve collaboration performance and provide an effective way to create a collaborative learning environment, which mainly based on recommendation, and refers to learner profile and evaluations.

Table 12. Relationship Between the Personal Profile and the Extent of School Roles among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents in terms of Cooperative Learning

Profile	Extent of Roles	χ^2 Value	p- Value	Decision	Interpretation
Age		11.040	0.026	Reject H_0	Significant
Gender		2.100	0.717	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
School Attended	Cooperative Learning	59.321	<0.001	Reject H_0	Significant
Awards		3.732	0.155	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Type of Civic Engagement		21.129	0.02	Reject H_0	Significant

In table 13, interpretation of not significant was evident in all aspects of the respondents' profiles. It implies that age, gender, school attended, awards, and type of civic engagement are not vital in the disciplining practices in the school.

In the study by Encina and Berger (2021), they focused on the moderating role of school climate to promote students' civic behaviors in their school. Their study followed the Authoritative School Climate Theory, where they proposed the two key dimension of school social climate namely, student support and disciplinary structure, which are relevant to explain students' civic engagement within their schools.

Table 13. Relationship Between the Personal Profile and the Extent of School Roles among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents in terms of Discipline Practices

Profile	Extent of Roles	χ^2 Value	p- Value	Decision	Interpretation
Age		2.901	0.574	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Gender		1.533	0.821	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
School Attended	Discipline Practices	25.861	0.258	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Awards		0.619	0.734	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Type of Civic Engagement		10.826	0.371	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant

In table 14, relationship between the personal profile and the extent of school roles among the graduates of public secondary school respondents in terms of academic success was evident in components such as school attended and the type of civic engagement. It implies that the school a student attends can have profound implication for their academic success due to differences in resources, teaching quality, curriculum, peer environment, and community support. Significant relationship was also established between types of civic engagement and academic success which means types of civic engagement contribute to academic success by promoting the development of the practical skills, enhancing critical thinking, increasing motivation and engagement, and fostering a sense of responsibility and connection to the community.

This research article by Moleko and Arko-Achemfuor (2021) found out that the Supplementary Learner Support Program SLSP improved the performance of the learners who participated in the program and their schools significantly.

Table 14. Relationship Between the Personal Profile and the Extent of School Roles among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents in terms of Academic Success

Profile	Extent of Roles	χ^2 Value	p- Value	Decision	Interpretation
Age		8.947	0.062	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Gender		4.326	0.364	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
School Attended	Academic Success	36.119	0.029	Reject H_0	Significant
Awards		3.884	0.143	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Type of Civic Engagement		26.039	0.004	Reject H_0	Significant

In table 15, the relationship between the personal profile and the extent of school roles among the graduates of public secondary school respondents in terms of grading system was evident in aspects such as age and school attended. This implies that the grading system of the school attended has a vital impact on the age of the respondents. The study tested the relative contribution of student support and disciplinary structure on students' civic behaviors, directly and interacting with their sense of belonging. A series of two-level hierarchical linear modeling analyses revealed that, after controlling for sex, school phase, school size, and school administrative dependency, student sense of belonging was positively related to civic engagement within their schools.

On the contrary, results from the study of Marohombsar (2021), disclosed that there is a relationship between the learners' profile and perceived effect of modular approach and their profile showed that the learners' perceptions are not significantly related to their profile.

Table 15. Relationship Between the Personal Profile and the Extent of School Roles among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents in terms of Grading System

Profile	Extent of Roles	χ^2 Value	p- Value	Decision	Interpretation
Age		11.076	0.026	Reject H_0	Significant
Gender	Grading System	2.667	0.615	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
School Attended		43.664	0.004	Reject H_0	Significant
Awards		2.405	0.300	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant

Type of Civic Engagement	10.068	0.435	Failed to Reject H _o	Not Significant
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In table 16, relationship between the personal profile and the extent of school roles among the graduates of public secondary school respondents in terms of social support in school was not evident, implying that the profile of the respondents was not affected by the social support the school is giving them.

Parallel to the study of (Sabado et al., 2024) despite differences across strands, age, and gender, the study concludes that these demographics do not significantly affect the perceived factors influencing school roles.

Table 16. Relationship Between the Personal Profile and the Extent of School Roles among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents in terms of Social Support in School

Profile	Extent of Roles	χ^2 Value	p- Value	Decision	Interpretation
Age		2.787	0.594	Failed to Reject H _o	Not Significant
Gender		4.885	0.299	Failed to Reject H _o	Not Significant
School Attended	Social Support in School	27.596	0.189	Failed to Reject H _o	Not Significant
Awards		2.392	0.302	Failed to Reject H _o	Not Significant
Type of Civic Engagement		6.967	0.729	Failed to Reject H _o	Not Significant

Table 17 shows the relationship between the personal profile and the extent of school roles among the graduates of public secondary school respondents in terms of other school activities particularly in the school attended. This implies that the school attended by the students can shape the range, quality, and accessibility of extracurricular and co-curricular activities, thereby influencing their overall educational experience and personal development.

From the study of Latif et al., (2020) results showed that in almost all comparisons, out-of-school and in-school active learners exhibited similar engagement levels, but these were much higher than low engagers. In addition, the implications of the findings for the enhancement and effective integration into school activities were presented.

Table 17. Relationship Between the Personal Profile and the Extent of School Roles among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents in terms of Other School Activities

Profile	Extent of Roles	χ^2 Value	p- Value	Decision	Interpretation
Age		5.444	0.245	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Gender		2.271	0.686	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
School Attended	Other School Activities	39.825	0.011	Reject H_0	Significant
Awards		1.996	0.369	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Type of Civic Engagement		11.103	0.35	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant

Relationship Between the Personal Profile and the Level of Civic Engagement among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents as Outcomes of School Roles

There is a growing need for increased civic engagement in developing countries. It was argued that civic education has not met the needs because it is uncritical, but it can be reformed through critical consciousness theory. However, for civic education reforms, there is a relationship between sociodemographic factors and civic engagement.

On this juncture, Ajaps and Obiagu (2012) investigated the influence of six sociodemographic factors, namely, gender, location, age, income, education, and ethnicity, on two civic engagement constructs which are environmental civility and community volunteering. Results of their study revealed that community volunteerism is influenced by age, gender, and location, while environmental civility is influenced by location and education, and there is a low level of civic engagement. The implications of these findings for a critical civic education aimed at increasing critical consciousness and civic actions.

Table 18 showed a relationship between the personal profile and the level of civic engagement among the graduates of public secondary school respondents as outcomes of school roles in terms of civic actions in aspects of school attended and awards. This implies that the civic actions have a great effect on the school attended where it can significantly shape their opportunities and experiences with civic action and the awards received of the learners plays a crucial role in honing the perception and impact of individual in the organization.

Table 18. Relationship Between the Personal Profile and the Level of Civic Engagement among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents as Outcomes of School Roles in terms of Civic Actions

Profile	Extent of Roles	x^2 value	p- Value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	Civic Actions	7.046	0.133	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Gender		0.926	0.921	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
School Attended		41.499	0.007	Reject H_0	Significant
Awards		6.373	0.041	Reject H_0	Significant
Type of Civic Engagement		9.821	0.456	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant

In table 19, the relationship between the personal profile and the level of civic engagement among the graduates of public secondary school respondents as outcomes of school roles in terms of civic commitment is evident in the aspect of gender. This implies that gender influences individuals' levels of civic commitment, the issue that they prioritize, and the strategies they employ to effect change within their communities.

To strengthen the result of the study, evidence not only shows differences in the political preferences of males and females but also shows males have higher probabilities of participating in political activities than females (Schlozman, 2012). Alternatively, female adolescents value their involvement in noninstitutionalized forms of participation (e.g., promotion of human rights, care of the environment, community support; Hooghe et al., 2015). Similarly, findings from the International Civic and Citizenship Education Study's (ICCS) Chilean sample show significant differences between male (72%) and female (80%) expectations of participating in volunteer activities (Schulz, Ainley, Fraillon, Kerr, & Losito, 2010).

Table 19. Relationship Between the Personal Profile and the Level of Civic Engagement among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents as Outcomes of School Roles in terms of Civic Commitment

Profile	Extent of Roles	x^2 value	p- Value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	Civic Commitment	8.481	0.205	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Age		4.306	0.635	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Gender		52.201	0.018	Reject H_0	Significant

School Attended	0.103	0.991	Failed to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
Awards	7.843	0.930	Failed to Reject H ₀	Not Significant

In table 20, the relationship between the personal profile and the level of civic engagement among the graduates of public secondary school respondents as outcomes of school roles in terms of civic skills is evident in the aspect of the school attended. This implies that the school attended by the learners can create a supportive learning environment, empowering students to become informed, engaged, and responsible members of society.

According to the study of LeCompte et al., (2020) data analysis suggests that iEngage, an action civics summer school, was effective in increasing elements of students' civic competence, including their ability to get people to care about a problem, organize and run a meeting, write an opinion letter, or contact a media outlet to express their views, and contact an elected official or community leader to address an issue.

Table 20. Relationship Between the Personal Profile and the Level of Civic Engagement among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents as Outcomes of School Roles in terms of Civic Skills

Profile	Extent of Roles	χ^2 value	p- Value	Decision	Interpretation
Age		9.039	0.171	Failed to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
Gender		4.172	0.653	Failed to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
School Attended	Civic Skills	49.502	0.032	Reject H ₀	Significant
Awards		1.737	0.629	Failed to Reject H ₀	Not Significant
Type of Civic Engagement		9.128	0.866	Failed to Reject H ₀	Not Significant

In table 21, the relationship between the personal profile and the level of civic engagement among the graduates of public secondary school respondents as outcomes of school roles in terms of social cohesion is evident in the aspect of awards. This implies that by valuing and celebrating the achievement of individuals within the community, awards contribute to a sense of belonging, connectedness, and collective well-being that has a positive implication for social cohesion.

In the study of Delfgaauw et al., (2020) team incentives may lead to more coworker support or to higher peer pressure and thereby, can affect the team's social cohesion.

Table 21. Relationship Between the Personal Profile and the Level of Civic Engagement among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents as Outcomes of School Roles in terms of Social Cohesion

Profile	Extent of Roles	χ^2 value	p- Value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	Social Cohesion	9.923	0.128	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Gender		2.806	0.833	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
School Attended		68.496	<0.001	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant
Awards		9.945	0.019	Reject H_0	Significant
Type of Civic Engagement		11.981	0.680	Failed to Reject H_0	Not Significant

Relationship Between the Extent of School Roles and the Level of Civic Engagement among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents as Outcomes of School Roles

In table 22, the relationship between the extent of school roles and the level of civic engagement among the graduates of public secondary school respondents as outcomes of school roles are tested and showed significant findings in all aspects except in other school activities. This implies that Cooperative Learning, Disciplinary Practices, Academic Success, Grading System, and Social Support in School has a vital role in performing civic actions.

In contradiction with result, findings in the study of Bauml (2022), revealed that participants who joined school activities like entering in camp believed that they are capable of making difference in their communities. Their ideas for youth civic action in schools and broader communities typically represented personally responsible and participatory notions of citizenship.

Table 22. Relationship Between the Extent of School Roles and the Level of Civic Engagement among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents as Outcomes of School Roles in terms of Civic Actions

Extent of Roles	Civil Engagement	ρ value	p- Value	Decision	Interpretation
Cooperative Learning	Civic Actions	.215**	<.001	Reject H_0	Significant

Disciplinary Practices	.197**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Academic Success	.269**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Grading System	.322**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Social Support in School	.257**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Other School Activities	0.034	0.566	Failed to Reject H _o	Not Significant

In table 23, the relationship between the extent of school roles and the level of civic engagement among the graduates of public secondary school respondents as outcomes of school roles in terms of civic commitment was tested and showed significant relationship on all components except for disciplinary practices. This implies that Cooperative Learning, Academic Success, Grading System, Social Support, and other school activities in School has a vital role in committing on civic engagements.

School roles can affect other important forms of political engagement. Civic education may affect civic norms, political knowledge, political efficacy, political attitudes, and political ambition (Torney-Purta & Wilkenfeld 2009, Gainous & Martens 2016, Green-Riley 2021, Kalla & Porter 2022).

Table 23. Relationship Between the Extent of School Roles and the Level of Civic Engagement among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents as Outcomes of School Roles in terms of Civic Commitment

Extent of Roles	Civil Engagement	ρ value	p-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Cooperative Learning		.196**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Disciplinary Practices		0.112	0.055	Failed to Reject H _o	Not Significant
Academic Success	Civic	.287**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Grading System	Commitment	.292**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Social Support in School		.305**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Other School Activities		.200**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant

Table 24 shows the relationship between the extent of school roles and the level of civic engagement among the graduates of public secondary school respondents as outcomes of school roles in terms of civic skills. All the school roles have a significant effect on the civic skills of the respondents implying that civic skills adopted were product of the school roles. It was stated that giving substantial promise to educational institutional leaders, educators, and their students when it emerges provides students with the best chance to gain skills and capacities enriched with ethics, empathy, and compassion in

becoming effective leaders of tomorrow. Moreover, teaching them the significance of accountability, the importance of service learning, and the necessity for demonstration of ethos, compassion, and empathy, cultivate the sense of belonging while building on awareness, interaction, and leadership mindsets (Grigoropoulos, 2020).

Table 24. Relationship Between the Extent of School Roles and the Level of Civic Engagement among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents as Outcomes of School Roles in terms of Civic Skills

Extent of Roles	Civil Engagement	ρ value	p-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Cooperative Learning	Civic Skills	.163**	0.005	Reject H _o	Significant
Disciplinary Practices		.194**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Academic Success		.309**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Grading System		.293**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Social Support in School		.292**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Other School Activities		.164**	0.005	Reject H _o	Significant

In table 25, the relationship between the extent of school roles and the level of civic engagement among the graduates of public secondary school respondents as outcomes of school roles in terms of social cohesion is evident in all aspects. This implies that all the school roles are vital in engaging in social cohesions. The development of the knowledge and skills of students can only be complete when the tenets of civic engagement are inculcated in them to respond to the needs of society (Owusu- Agyeman and Fourie- Malherbe, 2021).

Table 25. Relationship Between the Extent of School Roles and the Level of Civic Engagement among the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents as Outcomes of School Roles in terms of Social Cohesion

Extent of Roles	Civil Engagement	ρ value	p-Value	Decision	Interpretation
Cooperative Learning	Social Cohesion	.238**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Disciplinary Practices		.184**	0.002	Reject H _o	Significant
Academic Success		.261**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Grading System		.351**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Social Support in School		.277**	<.001	Reject H _o	Significant
Other School Activities		.125*	0.033	Reject H _o	Significant

Overall, the null hypothesis in this study was rejected and it was found that there were significant relationships that existed between and among variables that were taken into consideration in this study.

Meaningful Experiences of the Graduates of Public Secondary School Respondents Relevant to their Civic Engagement

Experiences of the graduates of public secondary school respondents which are relevant to their civic engagements varies differently for every respondent. Some might have combinations of the engagements which they point to have rooted from their high school experiences.

For a more detailed analysis, the author used thematic analysis. Thematic analysis is a method of qualitative data analysis. It is a useful and accessible tool for qualitative researchers. Thematic analysis is the method under a variety of epistemological frameworks. Codes and themes were used to describe the framework for conducting the analysis (Kiger and Varpio, 2020). In this part, each theme was highlighted using quoted responses of the respondents.

The researcher of the study used the types of civic engagement they are involved in as the themes. Upon carefully analyzing the answers, the highest number of responses were coded as activism and advocacy. Activism and advocacy focus on the things that the respondent is engaged in and is based on his current activities and routines. The succeeding statement is presented to strengthen respondents' civic engagement.

“Sa paaralan natutunan kong magplano at mag- isip ng sistematiko na nagagamit ko ngayon sa aking trababaho.”

“Nagagamit ko ang mga natutuhan ko sa paaran lalo na pagdating sa pakikipag-usap at humarap ng ayos sa mga tao”

“Nagsusulong ako ng adbokasiya tungkol sa pataas na pagtingin sa mga kababaihan at kalalakihan. Pinapahalagahn ko rin ang mga miyembro ng LGBTQA.”

“Nagsusulong ako ng mga adbokasiya tungkol sa pag-iingat at pagpepreserve ng aming kapaligiran, upang makilala rin ito bilang isang tourist spot. “

Another theme is Community Education and Awareness which is characterized by the activities and involvement to programs which promotes educating the community. The following are some statements from the respondents:

“Naituro sa akin ng paaralan kung paano makinig at magbahagi rin ng aking kaalaman sa aking mga ka-barangay.”

“Nagsusulong ng mga adbokasiyang pangkabuhayan upang mas makilala pa ang aming produktong kape hindi lamang dito sa Laguna maging sa buong mundo.”

“Bilang isang guro sinisikap kong maturuan ang aking mga mag-aaral kung paano magiging mabuting mamamayan ng ating bansa.”

“Nagsasagawa kami ng mga trainings upang makatulong sa pagpapaunlad ng buhay ng mga taong nasasakupan namin.”

Another theme featured is Political Engagement. More than exercising the right to vote, this theme depicted activities of the respondents which showcased them as public servants. Political engagement is an application of what they have known during their high schools and was mostly widened by their own experiences. This were highlighted with these responses:

“Sa paaralan nahubog ang kakayahan kong maging isang mabuting leader, kaya naman nagagamit ko ito ngayon bilang isang lingkod bayan.”

“Malaki ang naitulong sa akin ng pag-aaral sa public school. Natulungan ako ng paaralan lalo na sa problem solving na nagagamit ko ngayon bilang isang lingkod bayan.”

“Noong ako ay high school pa mahilig ako sumali sa mga activity sa school. Kaya naman ngayon bilang barangay official, gusto ko na laging lumalahok sa mga programa ang aming barangay.”

“Suportahan ang mga programang isinusulong ng aming SK Chairman at maging mabuting modelo sa kapwa ko kabataan.”

“Pagboto ng tama ang pinakamakabuluhang nagawa ko para sa aking bansa.”

“Ang pagpili ng mga tamang tao na ihahalal.”

Community Service and Volunteerism sparked in many of the respondents. Their act of service to various activities, especially during calamities, is outstanding. Claims includes these statements:

“Ang aming kapatarin ay nagsasagawa ng mga medical missions at nag volunteer din kami sa tuwing may mga Brigada Eskwela.”

“Bilang isang barangay volunteer ang hindi ko makakalimutang karanasan ko ay ang pakikiisa ko sa bayanihan tuwing mayroong mga sakuna o kalamidad.”

“Sa tuwing may mga sakuna o kalamidad ako ay nakikiisa bilang isang volunteer upang mag rescue dahil natutuhan ko sa paaralan ang tungkol sa mga first aid.”

“Bilang isang pulis ang pinakamakabuluhang karanasan ko ay pagsilbihan ang aking komunidad maging buhay ko man ang kapalit nito.”

The last theme is the Philanthropic Works and Fund-Raising Activities. These are some notable answers from the respondents who do not want to expose their identities as philanthropists, also those who are working for a good cause. Their responses are as follows:

“Nahubog ng paaralan ang aking pagkatao, naging bukas palad din ako sa lahat ng ngangailangan.”

“As part of our requirement during our senior years, we conducted gift giving and feeding program. After we graduated, we are still doing it to serve/ help the community.”

“I joined different fund-raising activities like fun run, food for a cause, zumba for a cause, which will benefit my community.”

“Sa tuwing may programa ang aming community, ako ay nagdo- donate ng pera na abot ng aking kakayahan dahil alam ko na makakatulong ito upang mas mapaunlad pa ang aming komunidad.”

These responses from the respondents strengthen the reliability and integrity that the school has well- established civic engagements to its learners through projects, programs, and activities.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made after finding some essential disparities that can also be the basis of future researchers.

1. Other profiles can be used as variables in the study.
2. Since the school was the setting for this study, future researchers can conduct a study to members of civic organizations, with different setting like their current work.
3. Future researchers may opt to study cultural awareness as result of the school experiences.
4. Results of this study can be presented to the top management of the Schools Division Office of Laguna to come up on a program intensifying civic engagements since it was found that these are significantly related to their previous school roles.

Compliance with the Ethical Standards

This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical standards and guidelines for research involving human participants. All participants provided written informed consent prior to their inclusion in the study, ensuring their voluntary participation and understanding of the research objectives, procedures and potential risks, and benefits. To maintain confidentiality, all personal data were anonymized. The data collected was securely stored and accessible only to the researcher. No financial or personal conflicts of interest were identified by the researcher in relation to this study. The researcher also

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